

early May. Individual plant selection was based on maturity, panicle length, grains per panicle, grain fertility, and grain acceptability (Table 1). The bulk population materials were as early as local cultivars. Some of them showed better seed fertility and grain numbers per panicle than local cultivars. Duration was about 90 d. The most promising materials are japonica/japonica crosses — Moroberekan/IRAT177 and ITA235/ Palawan. Lack of rain (108 mm) during Aug 1986 affected the reproductive and maturing stages.

Selected plants were sown 3 Oct 1986 to test cold tolerance at the vegetative stage. The transplanted crop was

Table 2. Cold tolerance of selected advanced lines of rainfed upland crosses. Malda, India, 1986-87.

Designation	Cross	Varietal group	Lines tested (no.)	Survival (%)	Average cold score (0-9 scale)	Range of cold tolerance
IR47687-10	IRAT104/Salumpikit	VI/I	3	12.5	7.0	7-7
IR47698-32	IRAT112/Sein Talay	VI/I	1	87.5	4.0	3-5
IR47688-78	IRAT112/Sein Talay	VI/I	6	45.8	7.0	5-9
IR47697-2	ITA235/IR9669 sel.	VI/I	6	62.5	5.8	3-9
IR47699-22	ITA235/Palawan	VI/VI	3	12.5	6.0	4-9
IR47699-28	ITA235/Palawan	VI/VI	2	56.3	5.5	5-6
IR47701-20	ITA235/UPLRi-7	VI/I	3	43.8	8.0	7-9
IR47705-6	Moroberekan/Palawan	VI/VI	8	64.5	6.7	5-9
IR47721-21	IRAT177/H.T. Boewani	VI/I	6	52.5	4.7	1-9
IR47724-14	Moroberekan/IRAT177	VI/VI	3	33.8	6.6	6-7
IR47730-4	IRAT112/Apura	VI/I	5	12.5	6.5	6-7
Soni	Local check			25.0	9.0	8-9
Dular	Local check			12.5	9.0	9-9

screened 3 Jan 1987. Average minimum temperatures were 18 °C in Nov and

13 °C in Dec. Table 2 shows crosses promising for survival percentage. □

Japonica and indica differences in large vascular bundles in culm

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We studied the number of large vascular bundles in the first internode from the

top (NLVBFI) and the number of primary branches of panicle (NPBP) at heading, in 45 indica (hsien) and japonica (keng) type varieties during 1981-82. NLVBFI was 20.9 ± 6.3 for indica type and 10.1 ± 1.9 for japonica type (see table). NPBP showed almost no differences between the two types. The ratio for NLVBFI/NPBP for 10 indicas averaged 1.97 and ranged from

1.64 to 2.27. The ratio for 10 japonicas averaged 1.13 and ranged from 1.02 to 1.19.

It seems that the ratio can be considered a new character to distinguish the two types. The difference in NLVBFI between the two types may relate to evolution and to nutrient transport. □

NLVBFI and NPBP^a in selected indica and japonica varieties. Hunan, China.

	NLVBFI		NPBP		A/B
	Average (A)	CV (%)	Average (B)	CV (%)	
<i>Indica</i>					
Guang-lu-ai 4	14.6	8.7	7.2	12.8	2.08
Yu-chi 231-8	15.5	8.7	8.0	8.8	1.94
Xiang-ai-zhao 9	18.1	6.1	8.2	15.0	2.21
Ke-zhen 145	27.5	9.1	16.0	5.6	1.69
Wei-you 6	24.1	16.0	12.0	5.6	2.01
Zhen-zhu-ai	22.7	13.6	11.4	9.4	1.99
Qui-chao 2	22.9	9.5	11.6	7.3	1.97
Qiang-yan 1811	18.7	8.7	9.6	11.1	1.95
Mi-yan 23	23.2	10.7	10.2	11.1	2.27
IR26	18.7	14.9	11.2	5.6	1.64
<i>Japonica</i>					
Tian-jin-yong	12.0	9.6	10.8	8.5	1.11
Long-hu 6	11.7	7.0	10.2	12.0	1.14
58 fu-nuo	8.3	9.9	7.0	19.0	1.18
177 fu-lei	10.7	15.7	10.5	14.3	1.02
6107	11.0	14.8	10.3	17.8	1.07
78-14	9.5	12.9	8.0	13.4	1.19
4001	10.3	20.9	9.2	25.2	1.12
Hai203	9.5	8.8	8.0	11.8	1.19
Yi-chang 105	11.6	10.8	10.6	15.4	1.09

^aMeans of 10 plants, including 5 main culms and 5 tillers. NLVBFI = large vascular bundles in first internode, NPBP = primary branches of panicle.

Grain quality and nutritional value

Correlation between rice grain and straw protein content and yield

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BR3 rice was grown at the Bangladesh Agricultural University Farm, Mymensingh, May-Oct 1982 with 4 treatments of ZnO (0, 2, 5, and 8 kg Zn/ha) and gypsum (0, 20,30, and 40